

Perceptions and Attitudes Regarding Depression among Medical and Nursing Students Studying in Mandya District, Karnataka – A Cross-Sectional Study

Harini K.C.¹, Keerthi B. Vishwanath², Vinay Muninarayanaswamy³, Bangalore Kumarappa Shivakumar⁴, Madhu Nagendraiah⁵, Manjushree Malkonahalli Srikanta⁶

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Sri Chamundeshwari Medical College Hospital and Research Institute, Ramnagar, Karnataka, India

²Junior Resident, Mandya Institute Of Medical Sciences, Mandya, Karnataka, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Mandya Institute of Medical Sciences, Mandya, Karnataka, India

⁴Professor & HOD, Department of Psychiatry, Sri Chamundeshwari Medical College Hospital and Research Institute, Ramnagar, Karnataka, India

⁵Anaesthesiologist, General Hospital, Maddur, Mandya, Karnataka, India

⁶Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Sri Chamundeshwari Medical College Hospital and Research Institute, Ramnagar, Karnataka, India

Received: 15-07-2024 / Revised: 02-08-2024 / Accepted: 10-09-2024

Corresponding Author: DR. Bangalore Kumarappa Shivakumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Approximately 280 million people in the world have depression. Depression is 50% more common among women. Suicide is the fourth leading cause of death in 15-29 year age group.

Barriers to effective care include lack of investment in mental health care, lack of trained health-care providers and social stigma. Lack of mental health training among PHC doctors is the leading cause for under diagnosis of patients with depression. The perceptions and attitudes of health professionals is a direct outcome of the type of mental health training they have undergone.

To improve the management of depression in the community, two group of health care persons i.e., doctors and nurses should have adequate knowledge and attitude towards depression. Hence, study on the assessment of perceptions and attitudes towards depression is thus needed.

Methods: A cross sectional study was done after obtaining informed consent. The study participants were adults (>18 years). We employed unknown population sample size formula with a population proportion of 50%, relative error of 10% and a confidence interval of 95%. The sample size required was 384. Convenience sampling method was used. Data was collected by interview method by using semi-structured pre-tested questionnaire. It has three sections. The first collected socio-demographic information. The second comprised questions to assess knowledge about various aspects of depression. The third section utilized the Depression attitude questionnaire (DAQ). Data was analysed in MS Excel software. Categorical data were described using frequencies and proportions. Mean and standard deviation was used to describe quantitative data. Z – test for two population proportion was used to determine difference between the frequencies. A p-value of 0.05 or less was considered statistically significant.

Results: Out of 458 students, 217 were medical and 241 were nursing students. 63.6% of the medical students (n=138) felt that about 10% of the adult population suffer from depression, while 74.7% of the nursing students (n=180) felt about 5% of the adults suffer from depression. The difference is significant.

A substantial proportion of medical (84.3%) and nursing (75.5%) students think that depression is a more significant problem. 125 medical (57.6%) and 88 nursing students (36.5%) consider young adults to be vulnerable to depression. 78.3% of medical (n=170) and 66.0% of nursing students (n=159) identify the elderly as a demographic at risk for depression. 159 (73.3%) medical and 142 (58.9%) nursing students knew that females were more at risk of depression compared to males. A majority of medical (83.4%, n=181) and nursing students (69.3%, n=167) believe that depression is more common among urbanites.

Conclusion: The gaps in knowledge is different for medical and nursing graduates. A good number of nursing students believed majority of the depression cases originated from recent misfortune. Discriminatory attitudes and stigma has been shown to limit depressed patients to seek help. Variations in perceptions on depression is strongly influenced by social and cultural factors. The nursing students held more of a compassionate attitude. Majority of the respondents preferred depressed patients to be managed by specialist and anti-depressants produces satisfactory result. If we provide adequate training in mental health to nursing and medical graduates, they can provide better mental health services.

Keywords: Perceptions, Attitudes, Depression, Medical and nursing students.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Depression is a common mental health condition that can happen to anyone. It is characterized by a low mood, loss of pleasure or interest in activities for long period of time. This is different from regular mood changes and feelings about everyday life. Depressive episodes last most of the day, nearly every day, for at least two weeks. People with depression may experience disturbed sleep and changes to their appetite. They may have feelings of low self-worth, thoughts about dying, hopelessness about the future. Tiredness and poor concentration are also common. [5]

Depression results from a complex interaction of social, psychological and biological factors. People who have lived through abuse, severe losses or other adverse events are more likely to develop depression. Depression can cause difficulties in all aspects of life, including work performance, relationships with family, friends and community. There is a strong relationship between depression and physical health, including cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes and respiratory diseases. People with depression are at increased risk of suicide. [2]

Approximately 280 million people in the world have depression. About 3.8% of the population experience depression, including 5% of adults and 5.7% of adults older than 60 years. Depression is 50% more common among women. 10% of pregnant and post-partum women experience depression. [1] Around 700,000 people die due to suicide every year. Suicide is the fourth leading cause of death in 15-29 year age group. [1]

Prevention programs reduce depression. There are effective psychological treatments and medications for depression. However, these are often absent or inaccessible to more than 75% of the people, especially in low and middle-income countries. Barriers to effective care include a lack of investment in mental health care, lack of trained health-care providers and social stigma associated with mental disorders. [1,2]

Lack of mental health training among PHC doctors is the leading cause for under diagnosis of patients with depression. [3] Although the nurses had adequate knowledge, a majority of them were stigmatized and held negative attitudes towards mental illness. [6] It is noticed that, the perceptions and attitudes of health professionals is a direct outcome of their clinical exposure and the type of mental health training they have undergone. [4]

To improve the diagnosis and management of depression in the community, two groups of health care persons, that is doctors and nurses should have adequate knowledge and attitude towards depression. A study on the assessment of perceptions and attitudes towards depressive disorders is thus very much needed.

This study evaluates the differences in gaps in perceptions and attitudes regarding depression among doctors and nurses. And thus this study helps us to understand the difficulties faced by nurses and doctors for managing patients with depression.

Objectives

1. To study and compare perceptions and attitudes regarding depression among medical students.
2. To study and compare perceptions and attitudes regarding depression among nursing students

Materials and Methods

Study Design: We conducted this cross sectional study among medical and nursing students studying in Mandya, Karnataka. This study was conducted between February and June of 2024.

Study Participants and Setting: The study participants were third and fourth year medical and nursing students studying in various colleges in Mandya district of Karnataka state, South India. They were adults (>18 years) and those who consented to participate in the study were included.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique: As we were unable to find any recent similar study in and around Mandya district, We employed the unknown population sample size formula with a population proportion of 50%, relative error of 10% and a confidence interval of 95%. The sample size required was calculated to be 384 participants. Convenience sampling method was used. Data was collected by interview method.

Study Instruments: The semi-structured pre-tested questionnaire was used to collect data. It consisted of three sections. The first section collected socio-demographic information. The second section comprised questions to assess their knowledge regarding various aspects of depression. The third section utilized the Depression attitude questionnaire (DAQ) to evaluate their attitudes towards depression.

Statistical Analysis: Data was entered and analysed in MS Excel software. Categorical data were described using frequencies and proportions. Mean and standard deviation was used to describe quantitative data. Z – test for two population proportion was used to determine difference between the frequencies. A p-value of 0.05 or less was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 458 students participated in the study. 217 were medical students and 241 were nursing students. Of the 217 medical students, 142 (52.4%) were male and 129 (47.6%) were female. 193 (71.2%) were urban residents and 78 (28.8%) were rural residents. Of the 241 nursing students 57 (23.7%) were male and 184 (76.3%) were female; 93 (38.6%) were urban residents and 148 (61.4%) were rural residents.

None of the respondents had been diagnosed with depression. 10 (4.6%) medical and 6 (2.5%) nursing students knew a person among their family/friends who had been diagnosed with depression.

63.6% of the medical students (n=138) felt that about 10% of the adult population suffer from depression, while 74.7% of the nursing students (n=180) felt that it was about 5% of the adults. The difference in perception was significant. A substantial proportion of medical (84.3%) and nursing (75.5%) students think that depression is becoming a more significant problem.

125 medical students (57.6%) and 88 nursing students (36.5%) consider young adults to be vulnerable to depression. 78.3% of medical students (n=170) and 66.0% of nursing students (n=159) identify the elderly as a demographic at risk for depression.

159 (73.3%) medical and 142 (58.9%) nursing students knew that females were more at risk of depression compared to males. A majority of medical students (83.4%, n=181) and nursing students (69.3%, n=167) believe that depression is more common among urbanites. Over 60% of both medical (60.8%, n=132) and nursing (62.2%, n=150) students agree that education level is not a factor in determining susceptibility to depression.

Table 1: Perceptions regarding symptoms of depression

Sl no	Symptoms of Depression	Total Participants (n=458)	Medical Students (n=217)	Nursing Students (n=241)	Significant Difference
1	Lack of interest	378 (82.5%)	186 (85.7%)	192 (79.7%)	Yes
2	Persistent Sadness	394 (86.0%)	174 (80.1%)	220 (91.3%)	Yes
3	Low self-worth	336 (73.4%)	181 (83.4%)	155 (64.3%)	Yes
4	Hopelessness	326 (71.2%)	145 (66.8%)	181 (75.1%)	Yes
5	Decreased sleep	299 (65.3%)	137 (63.1%)	162 (67.2%)	No
6	Excessive guilt	294 (64.2%)	115 (53.0%)	179 (74.2%)	Yes
7	Slow thought & action	280 (61.1%)	162 (74.7%)	118 (49.0%)	Yes
8	Suicidal thoughts	265 (57.9%)	108 (49.8%)	157 (65.1%)	Yes
9	Weight loss	217 (47.4%)	84 (38.7%)	133 (55.2%)	Yes
10	Increased sleep	195 (42.6%)	99 (45.6%)	96 (39.8%)	Yes

Table 2: Participants' responses to Depression Attitude Questionnaire

Sl	Statement	Total Participants (n=458)	Medical Students (n=217)	Nursing Students (n=241)	Significant Difference
1	During the last 5 years I have seen an increase in the number of patients presenting with depressive symptoms	292 (63.8%)	166 (76.5%)	126 (52.3%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=11.301
2	Majority of the depression cases originated from recent misfortune	368 (80.3%)	157 (72.4%)	211 (87.6%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=8.497
3	Biochemical abnormality is the basis of severe depression	260 (56.8%)	170 (78.3%)	90 (37.3%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=18.563
4	It is possible to distinguish 2 groups of depression, one psychological in origin and the other caused by biochemical mechanisms	231 (50.4%)	133 (61.3%)	98 (40.7%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=9.214
5	Depressed patients are more likely to have experienced deprivation in early life than other people	281 (61.4%)	177 (81.6%)	104 (43.2%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=4.697

6	Becoming depressed is a way that people with poor stamina deal with life difficulties	276 (60.3%)	127 (58.5%)	149 (61.8%)	No (p=0.131) Z=1.507
7	Becoming depressed is a natural part of becoming old	167 (36.5%)	111 (51.2%)	56 (23.2%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=12.954
8	Patients with depression are discriminated by general public and avoided	211 (46.1%)	119 (54.8%)	92 (38.2%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=7.442
9	It is difficult to differentiate between unhappiness or a clinical depressive disorder that needs treatment	131 (28.6%)	48 (22.1%)	83 (34.4%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=6.109
10	Depression reflects a characteristic response which is not amendable to change	90 (19.7%)	41 (22.6%)	49 (20.3%)	No (p=0.211) Z=1.253
11	Anti-depressants usually produce satisfactory result in the treatment of depressed patients in general practice	370 (80.8%)	192 (88.5%)	178 (73.9%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=8.355
12	Most depressive disorders improve without medication	251 (54.8%)	85 (39.2%)	166 (68.9%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=13.326
13	The primary health care worker could be a useful person to support depressed patients	348 (76.0%)	134 (61.8%)	214 (88.8%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=14.0
14	There is little to be offered to those depressed patients who do not respond to what primary health care workers to	116 (25.3%)	41 (18.9%)	75 (31.1%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=6.3
15	If depressed patients need antidepressants, they are better off with psychiatrists than with primary health care workers	261 (57.0%)	103 (47.5%)	158 (65.6%)	Yes (p<0.05) Z=8.165
16	Psychotherapy for depressed patients should be left to a specialist	348 (76.0%)	161 (74.2%)	187 (77.6%)	No (p=0.75) Z=1.778
17	If psychotherapy was freely available, this would be more beneficial than anti-depressants for most depressed patients	389 (84.9%)	194 (89.4%)	195 (80.9%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=5.345
18	I feel comfortable dealing with depressed patients	232 (50.7%)	68 (31.3%)	164 (68.0%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=16.413
19	Working with depressed patients is heavy going, tedious or difficult	336 (73.4%)	184 (84.8%)	152 (63.1%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=11.056
20	It is the rewarding to spend time looking after depressed patients	259 (56.6%)	86 (39.6%)	173 (71.8%)	Yes (p<0.01) Z=14.495

Discussion

Depression is a significant public health problem Worldwide. It is most common mental health disorder. There are lot of false beliefs on the risk factors and causes of depression. Under diagnosis of depression leads to increased morbidity. [7-9]

Perceptions and attitudes regarding various aspects of depression, like identifying a person with

clinical features of depression, causes and risk factors leading to depression, psycho-social factors affecting depression, different methods of diagnosis, different treatment modalities and its effectiveness should be known to everyone , especially the literate population. Amongst the educated people, especially those working in health care system like medical and nursing graduates must be aware about most common mental health

condition like depression. These health care professionals are usually the first point of contact for patients, and it becomes very much necessary for them to have adequate knowledge about depression.

Various research studies have shown that although the health personnel had knowledge, there were gaps in knowledge both in quality and quantity of awareness regarding the various aspects of depression. [10-15] Yet, We have noticed other research studies which have given results like health personnel had poor knowledge about most common health conditions. [4,16-19]

A substantial proportion of medical (84.3%) and nursing (75.5%) students think that depression is becoming a more significant problem. This is in line with recent WHO statistics, i.e., approximately 280 million people in the world have depression. About 3.8% of the population experience depression, including 5% of adults and 5.7% of adults older than 60 years. [3]

159 (73.3%) medical and 142 (58.9%) nursing students knew that females were more at risk of depression compared to males. This is in line with WHO statistics which states Depression is 50% more common among women. [3]

None of the respondents had been diagnosed with depression. 10 (4.6%) medical and 6 (2.5%) nursing students knew a person among their family/friends who had been diagnosed with depression. Which is in contrast to another study where >70% participants knew people diagnosed with depression.^[17]

Perceptions Regarding Symptoms of Depression:

When all participants are considered, the top 5 responses regarding symptoms of depression are persistent sadness, lack of interest, low self-worth, hopelessness and decreased sleep.

Medical students' top 5 responses differed by the presence of 'slow thought & action' and the absence of 'insomnia'.

Nursing students' top 5 responses differed by the by the presence of 'guilt' and the absence of 'low self-worth'.

While the responses of medical students were significantly higher for 4 symptoms, those of nursing students were significantly higher for 5 symptoms.

When we considered Participants' responses to Depression Attitude Questionnaire (DAQ), we noticed that medical graduates have seen increase number of patients presenting with depressive symptoms during the last 5 years (76.5%) as

compared to nursing students (52.3%) this is in line with other studies. [19]

A good number of nursing (87.6%) and medical (72.4%) students believed that Majority of the depression cases originated from recent misfortune. Similar findings have been reported in other studies. [20,21] In another study [7] nearly 70% of the participants thought that the majority of depression is due to recent misfortune. Most common life events which can lead to depression could be financial crisis, physical/sexual abuse, loss of loved ones, etc.

It is a very common thought that people with poor coping skills are usually ones who present with mental disorders [18,22] and It was noticed that majority of nursing (61.8%) and medical students (58.5%) believed becoming depressed is a way that people with poor stamina deal with life difficulties. 81.6% of medical and 43.2% of nursing students believed depressed patients are more likely to have experienced deprivation in early life than other people.

Around half of medical and slightly more than a quarter of nursing students believed patients with depression are discriminated by general public and avoided. Discriminatory attitudes and stigma associated with depression has been shown to limit depressed patients to seek help.^[23,24]

Very few medical (22.1%) and (34.4%) of nursing students felt it's difficult to differentiate between unhappiness or a clinical depressive disorder that needs treatment.

Seldom medical students (22.6%) and nursing students (20.3%) had false beliefs like depression reflects a characteristic response which is not amendable to change. Variations in views and perceptions on depression may strongly be influenced by social and cultural factors.^[13]

Majority of medical students (78.3%) felt biochemical abnormality is the basis of severe depression as compared to nursing students (37.3%). There is significant difference. Most of medical students (61.3%) believed it is possible to distinguish 2 groups of depression, one psychological in origin and other caused by biochemical mechanisms, but only 40.7% of nursing students believed so. About half of medical and quarter of nursing students believed becoming depressed is a natural part of becoming old.

Most of medical (88.5%) and nursing 73.9% believed anti-depressants usually produce satisfactory result in the treatment of depressed patients in general practice. In the present study, although a vast majority disagreed, there were few respondents who believed that most depressive disorders improve without medication. This shows in terms of knowledge, in the present study the

medical graduates seemed to have a better knowledge than nursing students.

Most of the nursing students felt primary health care worker could be a useful person to support depressed patients since they act as first point of contact to most of the patients from remote places. But only two third of medical graduates supported this.

Around quarter of nursing and less than quarter of medical students believed there is little to be offered to those depressed patients who do not respond to what primary health care workers do.

In contrast around 65% of nursing students and 47% percent of medical students believed if depressed patients need antidepressants, they are better off with psychiatrists than with primary health care workers. Majority of the respondents preferred depressed patients to be managed by specialist. Similar findings were seen in other studies. [7,13,25,26]

Three fourth of participants of present study, felt psychotherapy for depressed patients should be left to a specialist.

Slightly more than two third of respondents supported that if psychotherapy was freely available, this would be more beneficial than antidepressants for most depressed patients.

In present, although 85% medical students 63 % of nursing students held negative attitudes towards depressed patients, and they felt working with depressed patients is heavy going, tedious or difficult, significant difference was observed in the different domains.

In present study, majority of nursing students felt comfortable dealing with depressed patients and they also felt it is rewarding to spend time looking after them. On a more general outlook, the nursing students held more of a compassionate attitude towards patients with mental health issues than medical students. This is in line with findings from another study. [27]

In united kingdom, a study done by Haddad et al., reported that if nurses in general practice were provided adequate training in mental health, they could provide much better mental health services. Supporting findings of other studies. [28-32]

Conclusion

With respect to above discussion we can conclude that, although both medical and nursing graduates have good knowledge over the prevalence, symptomatology regarding depression and its treatment, there is still scope for improvement over other aspects as well. And the gaps in knowledge over various aspects of depression is different for medical and nursing graduates.

A fairly good number of nursing students believed Majority of the depression cases originated from recent misfortune and also believed becoming depressed is a way that people with poor stamina deal with life difficulties.

Around half of medical and slightly more than a quarter of nursing students believed patients with depression are discriminated by general public and avoided. Discriminatory attitudes and stigma associated with depression has been shown to limit depressed patients to seek help. Variations in views and perceptions on depression may strongly be influenced by social and cultural factors.

Majority of the respondents preferred depressed patients to be managed by specialist and antidepressants usually produce satisfactory result in the treatment of depressed patients in general practice. Three fourth of participants of present study, felt psychotherapy for depressed patients should be left to a specialist.

In present, although 85% medical students 63 % of nursing students held negative attitudes towards depressed patients, and they felt working with depressed patients is heavy going, tedious or difficult, significant difference was observed in the different domains. On a more general outlook, the nursing students held more of a compassionate attitude towards patients with mental health issues than medical students.

If we provide adequate training in mental health to nursing and medical graduates, they could provide much better mental health services.

Limitations: Purposive sampling method was used hence these results may not be a representation of rest of the country.

Implications: To improve the knowledge, perceptions and attitudes of medical and nursing graduates towards depression, educational interventional programs are necessary. This is linked to better diagnosis and management of depressed patients.

References

1. https://www.who.int/health-topics/depression#tab=tab_1
2. https://www.who.int/health-topics/depression#tab=tab_2
3. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/depression>
4. Cowan J, Raja S, Naik A, Armstrong G. Knowledge and attitudes of doctors regarding the provision of mental health care in Doddaballapur Taluk, Bangalore Rural district, Karnataka. International journal of mental health systems. 2012 Dec;6:1-8.
5. Sreeraj VS, Parija S, Uvais NA, Mohanty S, Kumar S. Indian nursing students' attitudes

- toward mental illness and persons with mental illness. *Industrial psychiatry journal*. 2017 Jul 1;26(2):223-7.
6. Cruz HA, Mariano MP. Knowledge, attitude and practices (KAP) of nursing staff regarding depressive disorders in a private hospital in Quezon City, Philippines. *Health Sciences Journal*. 2019;8(1):10-9.
 7. Mbatia J, Shah A, Jenkins R. Knowledge, attitudes and practice pertaining to depression among primary health care workers in Tanzania. *International Journal of Mental Health Systems*. 2009 Dec;3:1-6.
 8. Mahmood-Abadi HZ, Kayhani M, Rabi M, Mohammadi MR. A survey of knowledge and attitude of non-psychiatrists (medical specialists) treating major depression. *Thrita*. 2012;1 (1):30-.
 9. James BO, Jenkins R, Lawani AO. Depression in primary care: the knowledge, attitudes and practice of general practitioners in Benin City, Nigeria. *South African Family Practice*. 2012;54(1):55-60.
 10. Mulango ID, Atashili J, Gaynes BN, Njim T. Knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding depression among primary health care providers in Fako division, Cameroon. *BMC psychiatry*. 2018 Dec;18:1-9.
 11. Aydın N, Yigit A, Inandi T, Kirpinar I. Attitudes of hospital staff toward mentally ill patients in a teaching hospital, Turkey. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*. 2003 Mar; 49(1):17-26.
 12. Loh DA, Joshi A, Taku K, Mendelsohn N, Katz CL. Knowledge and attitudes towards clinical depression among community medical providers in Gujarat, India. *Psychiatric Quarterly*. 2018 Jun;89:249-59.
 13. Ndeti DM, Khasakhala LI, Mutiso V, Mwayo AW. Knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP) of mental illness among staff in general medical facilities in Kenya: practice and policy implications: original. *African journal of psychiatry*. 2011 Jul 1;14(3):225-3 5.
 14. Chaudhary RK, Mishra BP. Knowledge and practices of general practitioners regarding psychiatric problems. *Industrial psychiatry journal*. 2009 Jan 1;18(1):22-6.
 15. Badrakalimuthu VR, Sathyavathy VR. Mental health practice in private primary care In rural India: a survey of practitioners. *World Psychiatry*. 2009 Jun;8(2):124.
 16. Alvi T, Hussain S, Laghari AA. Medical Professional's Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) of Depressive Disorder in Pakistan. *Majmaah Journal of Health Sciences*. 2015 Apr;216(2672):1-6.
 17. Almanzar S, Shah N, Vithalani S, Shah S, Squires J, Appasani R, Katz CL. Knowledge of and attitudes toward clinical depression among health providers in Gujarat, India. *Annals of Global health*. 2014 Mar 1;80(2):89-9 5.
 18. Y, Birhanu Z, Agenagnew L, Anand S, Yitbarek K, Ahmed G, Getnet M, Tucho GT. Knowledge and attitude of health extension workers regarding mental health problems in Jimma Zone, Ethiopia: A cross-sectional study. *BMJ open*. 2022 Feb 1;12(2):e048381.
 19. Turki Y, Saleh S, Albaik S, Barham Y, van de Vrie D, Shahin Y, Hababeh M, Armagan M, Seita A. Assessment of the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) among UNRWA health staff in Jordan concerning mental health programme pre-implementation: a cross-sectional study. *International journal of mental health systems*. 2020 Dec;14:1-0.
 20. Norton JL, Pommié C, Cogneau J, Haddad M, Ritchie KA, Mann AH. Beliefs and attitudes of French family practitioners toward depression: the impact of training in mental health. *The International Journal of Psychiatry in Medicine*. 2011 Feb;41(2):107-22.
 21. Haddad M, Waqas A, Qayyum W, Shams M, Malik S. The attitudes and beliefs of Pakistani medical practitioners about depression: a cross-sectional study in Lahore using the Revised Depression Attitude Questionnaire (R-DAQ). *BMC psychiatry*. 2016 Dec;16:1-1.
 22. Armstrong G, Kermode M, Raja S, Suja S, Chandra P, Jorm AF. A mental health training program for community health workers in India: impact on knowledge and attitudes. *International journal of mental health systems*. 20 11 Dec;5:1-1.
 23. Mansouri N, Gharaee B, Shariat SV, Bolhari J, Yousefi Nooraie R, Rahimi-Movaghar A, Alirezaie N. The change in attitude and knowledge of health care personnel and general population following trainings provided during integration of mental health in Primary Health Care in Iran: a systematic review. *International Journal of Mental Health Systems*. 2009 Dec;3:1-7.
 24. Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration, National Association of County Behavioural Health and Developmental Disability Directors, National Institute of Mental Health, The Carter Centre Mental Health Program. Attitudes Toward Mental Illness : Results from the Behavioural Risk Factor Surveillance System. Atlanta; Centres for Disease Control and Prevention; 2012.
 25. Ohtsuki T, Kodaka M, Sakai R, Ishikura F, Watanabe Y, Mann A, Haddad M, Yamada M, Inagaki M. Attitudes toward depression

- among Japanese non-psychiatric medical doctors: a cross-sectional study. *BMC research notes*. 2012 Dec;5:1-8.
26. Street A, Center A. General practitioners knowledge and attitude towards anxiety and depression in Abu Dhabi. *The Middle East Journal*. 2006 Jan;4.
 27. Poreddi V, Thimmaiah R, BadaMath S. Medical and nursing students' attitudes toward mental illness: An Indian perspective. *Investigacion y educacion en enfermeria*. 2017 Jan; 35(1):86-94.
 28. Haddad M, Walters P, Tylee A. District nursing staff and depression: a psychometric evaluation of Depression Attitude Questionnaire findings. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 2007 Mar 1;44(3):447-56.
 29. Thapa P, Rawal N, Bista Y. A study of depression and anxiety in cancer patients. *Nepal Medical College journal: NMCJ*. 2010 Sep 1; 12(3):171-5.
 30. Odejide AO, Morakinyo JJ, Oshiname FO, Omigbodun O, Ajuwon AJ, Kola L. Integrating mental health into primary health care in Nigeria: management of depression in a local government (district) area as a paradigm. *Seishin shinkeigaku zasshi= Psychiatria et neurologia Japonica*. 2002 Jan 1;104(10):802-9.
 31. Dowrick C, Gask L, Perry R, Dixon C, Usherwood T. Do general practitioners' attitudes towards depression predict their clinical behaviour?. *Psychological medicine*. 2000 Mar; 30(2):413-9.
 32. F Furegato AR, Ferreira da Silva Candido MC, Lobo da Costa Jr M. Comparing knowledge and opinions on depression among nurses in the health services. *Revista de Salud Pública*. 2009;11:200-11.